

THE INSTITUTION OF REPRESENTATION IN CIVIL LAW: A LEGAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the institution of representation in traditional civil law. A comparative analysis of the representation institutions of the Roman-Germanic and Anglo-Saxon systems has been conducted, identifying their history, similarities, and differences. Additionally, the important features of civil law representation are explained scientifically.

Keywords. Legal representation, voluntary representation, acting on behalf of a third party, intermediation, power of attorney, commercial representation, principle of autonomy, principle of transparency, mandate contract.

The law of representation, which is a distinct institute of civil law in Uzbekistan, like many other civil law institutions, belongs to the continental legal system. Currently, in comparative jurisprudence, the analysis of differences between the Anglo-Saxon (Common Law) and continental (Civil Law) concepts is given special attention. However, the legal regulation of mutual civil-legal relations within the national law of countries belonging to the same legal family (legal system) has its own specific features. It should be noted that representation law is no exception in this regard. When examined from a perspective closer to the continental and English models, certain differences in the legal regulation of these relations become apparent, which may be of interest to comparative jurisprudence and Uzbekistan's civil law.

Literature Review and Methodology. To understand the historical foundations and legal norms of representation, this study analyzes the development process of representation law in the continental and English legal systems. The article includes an analysis of works by scholars such as R. Zimmermann and K. Zweigert, as well as Uzbekistan's civil legislation and international legal documents. The research methodology applied is the comparative legal analysis method.

Discussion. In modern civil law, in order to demonstrate certain differences in representation law across the continent, representation (authority) is classified based on the source of its origin. Accordingly, representation is divided into statutory representation, which arises on the basis of a normative provision, and voluntary (consensual) representation, which arises on the basis of an agreement [8, p. 319]. This classification is known to us from German, Dutch, and French law. In cases of consensual representation, the agent's authority may depend on the principal's consent. That is, in this case, the agent's right to create legal rights and obligations for the principal arises from an act (authority) granted by the principal.

The essence of statutory representation is characterized by the fact that the authority arises on the basis of law or a court decision (for example, the establishment of guardianship) and does not require an act of authorization by the principal. Statutory representation serves multiple purposes in law, and for this reason, this term covers several categories of representation. The most important of these include:

- Representation on behalf of minors and persons who do not have full legal capacity,
- Representation in corporate relations (actions of the management bodies of legal entities in the course of their commercial activities).

Furthermore, representation arising in connection with the regime of joint ownership, as well as representation due to necessity (acting in the interests of another person without a power of attorney – *negotiorum gestio*), falls under statutory representation.

In contrast, the institution of representation in English law primarily considers the concept of “agency” as originating from the will of the principal, and therefore, it is often equated with consensual representation in civil law. Although statutory representation (*agency by operation of law*) occurs in certain cases in English law, it mainly applies to spousal agency and agency by necessity. However, statutory representation as an institution for protecting individuals who have lost or have limited legal capacity does not exist in English law.

Today, consensual representation is a contractual institution in countries that follow the continental legal tradition, having undergone specific influences from business and commercial activities. In the modern business world, the function of consensual representation is to facilitate economic transactions by enabling participants to create legal consequences through the actions of other persons. The legal fact in such cases is the legal act expressing the principal’s consent. Accordingly, the defining characteristic of consensual representation is the objective manifestation of intent.

In contrast to the above, statutory representation is expressed regardless of the will of the principal. Consequently, statutory representation, which is designed to protect individuals who cannot acquire civil rights or assume obligations through their own actions, fundamentally differs from voluntary (consensual) representation.

Consensual representation is closely linked to the principle of legal autonomy, i.e., the freedom of will, whereby an individual determines which agent will act on their behalf and to what extent they will be granted authority. This characteristic explains why consensual representation exists independently in private law, separate from statutory representation. In international relations between economic entities, consensual representation holds significant practical importance. For this reason, it has consistently attracted the attention of comparative law scholars.

In the civil law of continental countries, voluntary representation is traditionally divided into **direct (real) representation** and **indirect (derived) representation**. Direct representation is considered general representation, and this classification has a **conceptual** character. In Uzbekistan’s civil law, **direct representation** includes **power of attorney and mandate contracts**, while **indirect representation** includes **agency contracts**.

In **direct representation**, the agent acts “on behalf of another person”, legally binding the **principal and the third party**, while the agent itself exits from the legal relationship between them. In **continental doctrine**, this is usually referred to as the “**transpersonal effect**”. In civil law, acting “**on behalf of another person**” means that the third party must know or should have known from the agent or the circumstances that they are entering into a contract with the **principal**.

In **indirect representation**, the agent **acts in its own name**, becoming a direct party to the contract with the third party.

To identify the **main ideas of these two mutually exclusive concepts**, it is necessary to examine the **historical origins** of representation in **continental legal tradition**. The historical analysis of the representation institution is outlined in **two of the**

most frequently cited works, namely: **R. Zimmermann's** *"The Law of Obligations: Roman Foundations of the Civilian Tradition"* [6] and **K. Zweigert and H. Koetz's** *"An Introduction to Comparative Law"* [7].

The **historical origins of most legal phenomena** in the **continental legal system** typically begin with **Roman law**. **Classical Roman law** did not recognize the **concept of representation**, i.e., the possibility of establishing **civil rights and obligations** through the **actions of another person**. According to the **principle of the personal nature of obligations**, expressed in the maxim "**alteri stipulari nemo potest**" (*no one can undertake an obligation on behalf of another*), neither **contracts for the benefit of third parties** nor **representation** was recognized as an independent legal category.

The **"Mandatum" contract**, which later became the prototype of **direct representation** in civil law, **did not grant** the agent (**mandatary**) the authority to establish **legal obligations** between the **principal** and **third parties**. Only in **exceptional cases** did **Roman law** recognize legal consequences arising from **the actions of an intermediary**. These cases can, to some extent, be compared to **direct representation**.

During the **Middle Ages**, the **legal theory of representation** did not develop **significantly**. However, in the **17th century**, legal scholars—particularly in the **Dutch-Roman jurisprudence** tradition—**developed the key aspects of representation** that remain legally significant today. Their approach often **contradicted** classical **Roman jurisprudence**.

First, they **formulated the concept of direct representation**, or **agency contract**, in which **the agent is removed from the contract** made **on behalf of another person**. This principle was implemented using the **Roman Mandatum contract**. However, this **contradicted Ulpian's principle** of "**alteri stipulari nemo potest**", thereby granting **individuals the ability to establish legal rights and obligations through the actions of another person**. This **breakthrough** is attributed to **natural law jurists** [7, p. 432].

The **most significant contribution** to the **development of direct representation** was made by the **Dutch scholar Hugo Grotius**, who was the **first to distinguish the agency contract from a contract for the benefit of a third party** [6, pp. 45–46]. This distinction **remains fundamental** in the **civil law systems of continental countries**.

R. Zimmermann describes this difference as follows: Contracts belonging to the same **general category** (contracts for the benefit of third parties and **direct agency contracts**) share the common feature that an independent **third party** acquires rights under an agreement between **two other parties**.

Representation occurs when **one person (agent)**, authorized by another (**principal**), **enters into a contract with a third party for the benefit of the principal**. As a result, the contract creates **legal effects between the principal and the third party**.

Thus, the **key difference** between **representation** and a **contract for the benefit of a third party** is that in representation, the **principal always becomes a direct party** to the contract made by the agent. The **agent merely acts as an intermediary** and does not become legally bound by the contract.

In another situation, a third party would only have the right to demand performance. They do not become a party to the contract; rather, the contract remains legally binding between the creditor and the debtor. That is, the obligation to perform the contract can only be imposed within the framework of agency legal relations. In civil law, it is not permitted to conclude a contract that not only benefits a third party but also imposes obligations on them.

If we analyze the intent of the participants in a legal relationship, it can be determined that the agent accepts the promise on behalf of the principal, while the debtor expresses their intent to act in the contract for the benefit of a third party. This line of reasoning led Hugo Grotius to the following conclusion: If a person acts on behalf of another to purchase an object, then the ownership right arises in the person on whose behalf the agent is acting.

Christian Wolff supplemented this conclusion by stating the following: If a contract is concluded by an intermediary acting on the instructions of the principal, then such a contract not only creates rights but also imposes corresponding obligations on the principal. To give legal force to the intermediary's actions, civil law required proper authorization.

In addition to its conceptual discoveries, the natural law school provided the substantive basis for the theory of natural law and justified the civil law principles of agency by declaring the principle of freedom of contract on which all contractual relationships are built. According to the civil law rules of continental European countries and Uzbekistan, an agent cannot obligate the principal solely on the basis of their authority.

For agency relations to arise, the continental legal system introduces a special requirement:

The agent must act on behalf of the principal and, therefore, must inform the third party that they are not acting on their own behalf but as an agent. This is known as the principle of transparency, which was partially introduced and justified by Hugo Grotius and the natural law school [6, pp. 46–47].

The principle of transparency is based on the autonomy of will. One of the key aspects of freedom of will is that a person has the right to freely determine with whom they enter into contractual relations. Contractual freedom cannot exist if the third party does not know whether the other party is acting for their own interests or as an agent.

Until the third party realizes that the other party is acting as an agent, they can only consent to a contract with the agent personally. The principle of transparency manifests itself in agency law as a defining characteristic of the concept of “acting on behalf of another person”.

It is not without reason that direct agency is considered a separate category (genus). The concept of “acting on behalf of another person” predates agency contracts and primarily defines the general characteristics of agency in civil law.

The incorporation of the concept of indirect agency into the civil law system was justified by its commercial convenience. The structure of acting on behalf of another person but in one's own name, without the possibility of legally altering the legal position of the represented party, serves certain economic purposes and remains free from transpersonal effects.

If a person enters into a contract in civil law in their own name, they become a party to the main contract, and as a result of indirect agency, no legal relations arise between the principal

and the third party. The agent assumes all rights and obligations in relation to the third party. If the third party is unaware that the contracting party is acting on behalf of another person, it creates a type of agency known as “hidden representation.”

The classic cases of indirect agency are found in the French concept of “commission”, which refers to intermediary relations, where the agent is referred to as a “commissioner” or “intermediary”. If a commission agreement is concluded between the parties, no contractual relations arise between the principal (committent) and the third party. The contract between the principal and the intermediary is still considered an agency contract, even though the intermediary acts as a full-fledged counterparty in relations with the third party. This remains true even if the third party knows that the intermediary is acting in the interests of another person and even if they know exactly whose interests are being represented.

From the above, it follows that intermediary relations qualify as indirect agency and cannot be classified as hidden (undisclosed) agency where the third party is completely unaware that the agent is acting in the interests of others.

The concept of an intermediary contract is legally established in Article 832 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Under an intermediary contract, one party (the intermediary) undertakes, at the request of the principal (committent), to conclude one or more transactions for a fee in their own name, but at the expense of the principal. The intermediary acquires rights and assumes obligations under the contract concluded with the third party, even if the principal was specified in the contract or directly engaged with the third party for contract execution.

The intermediary contract has been widely used in both national and international commerce, primarily for business purposes, and continues to be applied today. The field of legal studies provides the following economic justification for its origin:

Imagine that the company “Shoe Seller” (a footwear retailer) purchases a large volume of shoes from “Foot Factory” LLC (a manufacturer) and later sells them to other firms. In this scenario, “Shoe Seller” bears full business risk, such as a decline in product demand or lower market prices. If “Shoe Seller” wants to share this risk with “Foot Factory”, they may agree to operate under an intermediary contract. Under the intermediary contract, “Shoe Seller” sells the shoes to wholesale buyers in its own name, and as a result, the wholesale buyers acquire contractual rights only against “Shoe Seller”—not “Foot Factory”—even if the buyers know that “Shoe Seller” is acting in the interests of “Foot Factory”. However, if “Shoe Seller” is truly acting in the interests of “Foot Factory”, then all economic risks related to contracts with third parties fall entirely on “Foot Factory”, while “Shoe Seller” assumes only the risk associated with earning a commission (percentage of sales).

The intermediary contract has evolved into a more beneficial legal structure for formalizing economic relations in the supply chain compared to the distribution contract. Under a distribution contract, the distributor purchases goods from the owner, becomes the new owner, and therefore assumes all economic risks. In contrast, an intermediary merely performs their contractual obligations toward the principal and does not acquire ownership rights over the subject of the intermediary relationship (as indicated by the legal feature “acting at the expense of the principal” found in the definition of intermediary agreements). The intermediary receives their compensation proportionate to the volume of goods sold.

In intermediary relations, agency takes an indirect form because the agent (representative) acts in the interests and for the benefit of another person (the principal). However,

unlike direct agency, the agent typically does not create legal rights or obligations for the principal, because the agent themselves becomes a contracting party with the third party.

A key characteristic of agency, such as the ability to directly create legal effects for a non-contracting party (which applies to power of attorney and commission agreements), does not exist in intermediary relations.

The Dutch legal scholar H.L.Y. Verhagen refers to intermediary agreements as “mandate without power” [5, pp. 15–21].

Direct representation and indirect representation distinguish, in their fundamental legal meaning, who is legally bound to a third party. In direct representation, the legal consequences of concluding a transaction based on power of attorney mean that the transaction is concluded between the principal and the third party. In intermediary relations, however, the transaction is concluded between the intermediary and the third party. Both representation structures are based on the contractual concept of a personal legal nature, meaning that a contract only creates rights and obligations for its participants.

The continental legal system clearly separates the external and internal aspects of agency relationships. Mandate and intermediary contracts formalize internal relations between the principal and the agent. The external relationship between the agent and the third party is regulated by general provisions in the civil codes of European countries. In national civil legislation, this is regulated by Chapter 10 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, “Agency and Power of Attorney” (Articles 129–144).

This distinction in the continental system emerged in 1847 as a “discovery”, separating “power of attorney” as a special legal act granting a trusted person the authority to conclude transactions with third parties. Before the 19th century, this distinction had no independent legal role. It was assumed that the granting of power of attorney always originated from a contract and could not be separated from it. The French Civil Code still considers power of attorney only within the framework of a special contract [7, p. 434].

Yhering was the first to propose that the granting of agency power could be based not only on an agency contract but also on other contracts, such as an employment contract or a joint activity agreement. According to Yhering, the term “mandate” represents the internal side of an agency contract, while “agent” refers to its external side. Yhering emphasized that the two aspects are not necessarily dependent on each other, and their alignment is “purely coincidental”.

Some individuals may perform agency functions without being agents, just as there may be individuals with agency powers who are not acting as agents under a mandate contract [6, p. 15]. At the same time, Yhering maintained that the internal and external aspects of agency are simply elements of a single legal relationship—the mandate contract.

The final step in refining the concept of agency was taken by Laband. He distinguished between power of attorney and mandate, considering them two aspects of the same relationship but with independent legal nature. Although in practice, they often overlap, they remain separate concepts.

According to Laband:

- A mandate contract defines the agent’s obligations and their authority in relation to the principal.
- The act of granting power of attorney, however, provides the agent with the legal ability to bind the principal and the third party.

Laband proposed a clear distinction between these concepts. Thus, the duration and

scope of power of attorney (defining when the agent can legally alter the legal position of the principal) must be separated from the contractual obligations (determining what the agent must do).

Furthermore, Laband demonstrated that not only mandate and power of attorney should be distinguished conceptually, but also their legal consequences:

- An agent may have power of attorney but still fail to comply with their obligations under the mandate contract.

It is worth noting that Laband's early ideas later formed the foundation of Germany's "Procura" commercial legal institution. According to the 1861 German General Commercial Code, an agent registered as a Prokurist received predefined legal powers covering all commercial activities necessary for business operations. Even if restrictions were imposed in the principal-agent contract, and even if these restrictions were known to third parties, they had no effect on the agent's Procura powers [6, p. 24].

Laband's arguments later led to the formulation of the "abstraction principle" (Abstraktionsprinzip) or the "principle of independence" in German legal science. The most significant conclusion derived from this principle was that:

- An agent may legally exercise more powers towards a third party than those specified in the agency contract.

The recognition of mandate and power of attorney as two separate legal concepts had a profound impact on legal doctrine and practice. These rules were later codified in Germany, Switzerland, Sweden, Italy, Greece, Japan, and the Netherlands.

In English common law, agency had not developed as an independent legal concept until the early 19th century. Until that time, agency was an "unregulated phenomenon," with its rules scattered across other doctrines such as employer-employee relations, legal representation, property custody, debt collection, and accounting reconciliation [4, p. 3]. Sources on agency were not published until 1811 and 1812 [2; 3]. Many concepts of agency law, including the doctrine of undisclosed agency relationships and the doctrine of estoppel (as the legal basis for holding a principal liable for the actions of an agent without proper authority), were elaborated in the 19th century. Many concepts of agency law, such as the doctrine of undisclosed agency relationships and the doctrine of estoppel as the legal basis for liability beyond the actions of an authorized agent, were developed in detail during the 19th century.

The distinction between an agent's authority in relation to their principal and their external rights towards third parties was "not reasonably established" until 1925. Nevertheless, even in the 18th and 19th centuries, there were English court rulings that addressed legal situations involving the exceeding of authority. There was no doubt among English judges that an agent could act within their legal capacity while simultaneously violating obligations under the agency contract by acting contrary to the principal's instructions. Like continental legal theory, English law reached the same conclusion by resolving specific cases while applying a minimal level of systematization and conceptual interpretation, without the necessity of creating a practical hypothesis as proposed by Laband.

Today, the distinction between granting power of attorney (a unilateral act of will that grants authority to a person) and the agency contract is legally established in almost all modern civil codes of continental European countries.

In practice, as Zweigert and Koetz [7, pp. 435] noted, this theoretical distinction is of little significance, but it has influenced the structure of regulatory provisions. Rules regarding the

granting of authority, the scope of conferred rights, their duration, and ratification (the subsequent approval by the represented party of a transaction concluded outside the granted authority) are usually included in the general part of the civil code. The provisions of the general part on representation can rightly be considered the result of high legal abstraction. As a result of this approach, representation is regarded as a legal institution. At the same time, various types of agency contracts, typically mandate and brokerage, should be regulated separately. Thus, if a person is authorized to perform acts of representation based on a granted power of attorney, the legal relations arising in this regard are governed by the provisions of the general part on representation. If a person is authorized to perform acts based on both a concluded mandate contract and a granted power of attorney, then the resulting legal relations are governed both by the general part provisions and the specific provisions on mandate contracts.

This approach was initially applied in Germany and is also characteristic of countries such as the Netherlands, Switzerland, Sweden, Italy, Portugal, Greece, and Russia. In these countries, a clear distinction is made between an agent's authority and their contractual relationship with the principal. As a result, such legal systems consider authority as a unilateral act of the principal, expressing their intention to legally bind the agent directly. They also distinguish the contractual legal relationship between the principal and the agent, which defines the parties' rights and obligations in their internal relationship.

However, not all countries within the continental legal system follow this perspective. For theoretical reasons, in France, authority is considered only as one aspect of the agency agreement between the parties. In particular, Article 1984 of the French Civil Code views a person's authority to legally bind another as an external outcome of the mandate contract [1, p. 914].

The civil code provides a general definition of authority arising by law or personal will. Article 129 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the following:

A transaction concluded by one person (the agent) on behalf of another person (the principal) under an authority based on a power of attorney, law, court decision, or the document of a represented state body directly creates, modifies, or terminates civil rights and obligations for the principal.

An agent may not conclude transactions on behalf of the person who granted them authority either with themselves or with another person they simultaneously represent, except in cases of commercial representation.

The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 817, defines the concept of agency based on the principle of "acting on behalf of another person":

Under an agency agreement, one party (the agent) undertakes to perform certain legal actions on behalf of and at the expense of the other party (the principal). The rights and obligations arising from the transaction concluded by the agent directly accrue to the principal.

An agency agreement constitutes direct representation, meaning that the agent acts on behalf of another person in transactions, intending to alter the legal status of that person without changing their own legal status.

Chapter 10 of the Civil Code, titled "Agency. Power of Attorney", contains provisions developed for the entire institution of agency, which apply to other general issues of agency as well as specific matters related to the issuance of a power of attorney. These norms are legally aimed at regulating direct agency relationships and are considered fair not only for relationships arising from an agency agreement but also for those arising from a brokerage contract.

A person cannot conclude a transaction on behalf of another person based on an agency agreement. The Civil Code does not establish an obligation for the principal to issue a power of attorney. However, Article 820 of the Civil Code states that after the execution of the assignment, the agent is required to return the power of attorney to the principal without delay if its validity period has not yet expired. This implies that voluntary agency relationships in Uzbek civil law must be formalized through a power of attorney.

Regardless of whether the transaction concluded by the agent with a third party is based solely on a power of attorney or on both an agency agreement and a power of attorney, in Uzbek civil law, such a transaction creates, modifies, or terminates the legal rights and obligations of the principal.

An agent cannot conclude transactions on behalf of the person granting them authority in relation to themselves or in relation to another person for whom they simultaneously act as an agent, except in cases of commercial agency (Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 129, Part 3).

Article 133 of the Civil Code introduces commercial agency. A commercial agent is a person engaged in entrepreneurial activities who, on a regular and independent basis, concludes transactions related to business activities on behalf of entrepreneurs. According to the content of Article 133, the legal regime of commercial agency leads to the following legal consequences:

A commercial agent may simultaneously act as an agent for different parties in transactions if all represented persons have given their consent;

A commercial agent may act without a power of attorney;

A commercial agent is obligated to maintain confidentiality regarding known trade transactions, even after fulfilling the given assignment.

The concept of commercial agency as provided in Article 133, as well as the independence of commercial agency rules from power of attorney regulations, stem from the essence of these institutions (which is also reflected in the title "Agency. Power of Attorney"). Any agency relationship—whether based on a power of attorney, an agency agreement, or a brokerage contract—immediately falls under the effects of Article 133 of the Civil Code as soon as the agent is declared a business entity.

The institution of commercial agency is exclusively a product of the continental legal system. As previously noted, English law does not introduce any practical rules to recognize agency relationships as commercial and does not construct specific doctrines in this regard. In case law, agency relationships are regulated through a single general agency model.

Conclusion

The institution of agency holds significant importance in the civil law system of Uzbekistan and has developed as part of the broader continental legal system. The differences between Anglo-Saxon and continental legal systems and their impact on agency law represent an essential subject of comparative legal research. The legal and consensual (voluntary) forms of agency, as well as their sources and origins, exhibit distinctive features in Uzbek civil law.

In the modern commercial world, the primary function of agency is to facilitate economic transactions, allowing participants to create legal consequences through the actions of others. At the same time, understanding and applying the legal foundations of agency in Uzbek civil law are crucial for ensuring justice and efficiency in civil legal practice. Further research is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of the various forms of agency, their applications, and the prospects for the future development of agency law.

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